

Far-UVC Light for Inactivating Airborne and Surface Viral Particles Including Covid-19, Ebola, and Influenza

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It has been well established that waves of light have destructive and constructive participation in the life cycle of biological organisms. The Far-UVC range, 207nm-235nm has been proven to break down the protein spikes Covid-19 and other viruses depend on to attach to healthy cells and reproduce without causing injury to humans. Destroying the “spikey” protein inactivates the virus preventing it from collecting on surfaces and from reproducing if the viral particle enters a host’s body. Many companies across the United States and World already produce the lifesaving bulbs, known as excimer lights, and hospitals have been using the special sterilizing effects of these lights since 2017. ¹Installation of the 222nm Far-UVC lights in public places, ambulances, delivery trucks, and essential businesses would provide a safe and effective impediment to the spreading of Covid-19 and quickly “flatten the curve” on Coronavirus. Further, a LED can be easily made and fashioned into masks, faucets, and wide arrange of practical products.

¹ (USHIO, 2017)

I. DEFINITIONS

Human Safe: Normal exposure causes no lesions, burns, or abnormalities to exposed areas.

Eye Safe: Normal exposure causes no blindness, lesion, cataract, or tare to eyes.

Far-UVC: 207nm-235nm

II. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 outbreak is problematic in that it is an adaptable and quickly mutating virus making an over-arching vaccine and cure difficult to produce. One important feature common to the different forms of the virus is the reliance on spikey proteins on its outer shell to latch on to human and animal cells. These spikes bind to different cellular receptors such as the ACE2 or APN and then the virus injects its own DNA into the host cell and multiplies within. If the spikes could be destroyed, then the virus would not be able to attach itself and replication would become impossible. Recalling the well-known principle that ultraviolet (UV) light damages protein structures, a question was posed, "is there a spectrum of light out there that could effectively inactivate the virus without harming people or animals?" The answer to the above question came in the form of Far-UVC light that operates in the 207nm-235nm wavelength.² The problem then became finding the right materials to produce Far-UVC in a safe packaging. The ready-made solution came in the form of excimer lights that operate at 222nm using a combination of gasses and can already be purchased. Diamond and AlGan based semiconductors were discovered to be able to produce 235nm and 210nm wavelengths respectively and 220nm wavelength can be achieved by using a selenium coating as a band pass filter.

III. HOW IT WORKS

² (Buonanno, 2017)

All matter has a resonance frequency in which its atoms are held together in an equilibrium state. Waves of light that have a longer wavelength than the matter they are interacting with are "blocked" or reflected and if the wave of light has a shorter wavelength than the piece of matter that it is interacting with, it is able to pass right through. However, if the wave of light is operating at the same frequency and has higher energy then it collides with the atoms forcing them to break apart.

To better understand these phenomena, think of RF signals and satellite TV. If your dish is facing a concrete building the RF waves cannot get to your dish and you have no "signal". The RF waves are able to go through the atmosphere and light foliage with minimal loss however, on a rainy day your signal is in and out. Rain has a close resonance frequency as k-band frequencies causing loss in close ka and ku bands that the satellites operate at. The far-UVC spectrum is of the perfect length that it "slams" into the proteins that make up the spikes the viral particles use, but are long enough that they are not able to penetrate and cause damage to the human skin cells. So successful is this range in inactivating the virus, that the effective UV dose is $\geq 2 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$ for a success of $> 95\%$.³ LED

IV. LED MATERIAL

A material was needed that had semiconductor properties and was able to output the Far-UVC

range or 207-235nm in order for the resulting LED to be used near or on people without the need of PPE. This included the requirement that it be Eye Safe.³⁴ ⁵ 245nm-270nm are known to be as effective on the viral spikey proteins however, that range can cause skin and eye reactions to humans. Another concern with the higher UVC range is its possibility of creating ozone which is damaging to the human respiratory system. At 275nm the spikey protein is damaged but could recombine if the light source is removed too quickly.

The bandgap of the material needed to be determined. When energy matching the photon energy or bandgap of a material is applied, photons equal in wavelength are emitted. Using the following formula:

$$B\lambda(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k_B T} - 1}}$$

Where h is Planck's constant, C is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength in hertz, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and the frequency of 1350.4Thz (222nm)

The energy of the bandgap was determined to be $\approx 5.58eV$

The material then needed to be capable of energy output that would cover the area of 1m. The effective UV dose is $\geq 2 \text{ mJ/cm}^2$.³ UV dose is defined as UV dose $\mu\text{Ws/cm}^2 = \text{UV intensity } \mu\text{W/cm}^2 \times \text{exposure time (seconds)}$ ⁶ The time in seconds can be ignored in applications of continuous operation. Converting

to power output the minimum required output power is 200mW and will cover an area of 1m x angle of field of view of the LED.

Two materials already in use as semiconductors, with the band gap of around 5.54eV, and that would be able to handle the power requirements were found to be diamond and AlGan. The wavelength produced by diamond materials is at the high-end of the safe range at 235nm while the AlGan is in a safer range of $\sim 210\text{nm}$. A search was then conducted for a type of coating to act as a band pass filter to achieve a consistent output frequency. While both selenium and lead were found to be in range, only selenium can be safely used for the intended applications. The selenium coating acts as a bandpass filter allowing only frequencies of 220nm to be emitted through the lens. A further benefit to the selenium coating is it emits in the tolerance operating range of the already tested and approved excimer lights that operate at 222nm. The threat of errant harmful rays not contained in the LEDs packaging is fully mitigated by using the semiconductor materials that emit in the Far-UVC range.

V. CONCLUSION

Two available semiconductor materials were identified for the incorporation into an LED that can inactivate not only the Corona-family of viruses, but also Ebola and

³ (Buonanno, 2017)

⁴ (Kaidzu, 2019)

⁵ (Welch, 2018)

⁶ (UV Definitions, 2019)

influenza. The identified materials operate in known and tested ranges of light that are safe for people and their eyes. The production of these LEDs will be game changing for the fight against the current threat of COVID-19. The biggest effect will be felt by Ebola ravaged regions where the host can carry the virus for years as opposed to the 2 weeks estimated of Coronavirus. Incorporating a LED into a facemask that the afflicted and their caretakers can use will dramatically improve their quality of life. Hafnium and zirconia blends were found to have potential for this application and are being researched further.

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